

**Trends in the evergreen oaks dominance from assembled species distribution models:
assessing climate change in Western Europe**

Author list:

Javier López-Tirado, Federico Vessella, Bartolomeo Schirone & Pablo J. Hidalgo

López-Tirado, J. (javier.lopez@dbasp.uhu.es)¹

Vessella, F. (vessella@unitus.it)²

Schirone, B. (schirone@unitus.it)²

Hidalgo, P.J. (Corresponding author, pablo.hidalgo@dbasp.uhu.es)¹

¹ Department of Integrated Sciences, Faculty of Experimental Sciences, International Campus of Excellence of the Sea (CEIMAR) and Environment, Biodiversity and Global Change (CEICAMBIO), University of Huelva, Avda. Tres de Marzo s/n, Huelva-21071, Spain.

² Department of Agriculture and Forestry (DAFNE), Università degli Studi della Tuscia, Via San Camillo de Lellis, snc, 01100, Viterbo, Italy.

Abstract

Questions: Will evergreen oaks be harmed or favoured by the expected global change? How could they interact? What is the trend along the twenty-first century regarding dominance or codominance among evergreen oaks?

Location: Western Europe.

Methods: We analysed four evergreen oaks (*Quercus ilex* subsp. *ilex*, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*, *Q. suber* and *Q. coccifera*) by means of Species Distribution Models (SDMs). Three algorithms were used: Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt), Logistic Regression (LR) and Environmental Distance (EnvDis). Taxa occurrences were taken especially from the National Forests Inventories (NFI), whereas environmental data was retrieved from WorldClim 1.4 project. Present period and four future scenarios (RCP 4.5 2050, RCP 4.5 2070, RCP 8.5 2050 and RCP 8.5 2070) were studied. The latter were carried out by the average of thirteen Global Circulation Models (GCMs). Consensus maps were built taking into account AUC values, which also were necessary for validating the models. Finally, a map pointing out the dominance and codominance among evergreen oaks was developed.

Results: Evergreen oaks would be benefited from the forecasted environmental conditions according to our results. Due to their spread in Western Europe, evergreen oaks would find new suitable areas for growing, leading to an increment of mixed forests or, in other words, a raise in the codominance among them.

Conclusions: This work deals with the uncertain future on evergreen oaks facing climate change. The use of different algorithms and GCMs, as well as the high validation values obtained, confer robustness to this study. Oaks play a significant role in vegetation and forestry. Moreover, they are an important resource of income, especially *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. suber*. Our findings might be highly useful for understanding the dynamics of evergreen oaks; the first step for carrying out management programmes, aiming to conserve this natural heritage.

Keywords: Evergreen oaks; Species Distribution Models; forecasting; Climate change; Potential distribution; Assembled models; Codominance; Dynamics vegetation; Western Europe.

Abbreviations:

Species Distribution Models (SDMs)

Global Circulation Models (GCMs)

National Forest Inventory (NFI)

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)

Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP)

Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC)

Area Under the Curve (AUC)

Quercus ilex subsp. *ilex* (Qile)

Quercus ilex subsp. *ballota* (Qbal)

Quercus suber (Qsub)

Quercus coccifera (Qcoc)

Running head: Assembled SDMs of evergreen oaks in Western Europe.

Introduction

Climate change concerns the scientific community since the last decades. Extreme climatic conditions, such as rising mean temperatures and variation in rainfall patterns, are expected along the present century (IPCC 2014). The former is more correlated with plant traits than mean annual precipitation (Moles et al. 2014). As a response to these shifts, organisms could undergo adaptations if they keep genetic diversity enough. On the contrary, species with a poor gene pool could not adjust via phenotypic plasticity and consequently become extinct (Leakey & Levin 1996; Dirzo & Raven 2003; Thuiller et al. 2011; Matesanz & Valladares 2014). Plants are primary producers; therefore they are the baseline of the ecosystems conservation. *Quercus ilex* L. shows high ability to host microhabitats, essential issue for many living beings in the wild (Regnery et al. 2013). Nevertheless, human-induced habitat fragmentation occurs nowadays according to stakeholders, limiting the plastic and microevolutionary responses of plant species (Matesanz & Valladares 2014). In the Mediterranean region, it is projected a severe shift in the climatic conditions, hence the distribution of native oak forests can be affected. In the period 1966-2006, a given area of cork oak (*Quercus suber* L.) forest in Portugal was altered mostly to pines and eucalypt; trend that holm oak [*Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* (Desf.) Samp or *Q. rotundifolia* Lam.] followed towards agriculture (Acácio et al. 2016). In other cases, some oak species are favoured to the detriment of others. In Andalusia (Spain), *Q. suber* has been harmed when co-occurred with *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* (Costa Tenorio et al. 2005). On the other hand, it has been stated how anthropogenic changes in forest management has favoured *Q. suber* (cork exploitation) at the expense of *Q. canariensis* Willd. (Urbieto et al. 2008). Luckily, there are still forest restorations at different spatial levels (Jacobs et al. 2015). An example is *Abies pinsapo* Boiss. at local level in Southern Spain (López Quintanilla 2013). In these countries, *Dehesas* in Spain or *montados* in Portugal, are well-known seminatural oak pasturelands (Vicente & Alés 2006; Marañón et al., 2009; Alejano et al. 2011; Vericat et al. 2012). Tree density is low, mainly made up by *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*, whose sweet acorns feed high quality Iberian pigs. *Dehesas* are also cultivated in other cases supporting a significant economy in

the rural environment (Muñoz Álvarez 2010). Ecologically, tree canopy plays an important role in *dehesas*. Albedo and temperature can be increased in the ground (Godinho et al. 2016), modifying the distribution of some insects like ants (Ruiz et al. 1999; Reyes-López et al. 2003).

Four evergreen oaks were studied: the above mentioned *Q. suber* and *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*, plus *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* L. and *Q. coccifera* L. Differences in morphology, leaf decomposition, chemosystematic and genetic have been found within *Q. ilex* (Rafii et al. 1991; Michaud et al. 1995; Sadaka-Laulan & Ponge 2000; Lebreton et al. 2001; Lumaret et al. 2002; Peguero-Pina et al. 2014; de Rigo & Caudullo 2016). Moreover, from a bioclimatic, chorologic and vegetational point of view, both taxa are clearly separated (Musarella et al. 2012). Their distribution only co-occurs in some stands of the Cantabrian coast and Catalonia (Spain) and Languedoc (France). Ecologically, subsp. *ilex* shows stricter water and temperature requirements than subsp. *ballota* (López de Heredia et al. 2007). The former has a closer link to areas under an oceanic influence, whereas the latter prefers inland zones. Therefore, there are sufficiently enough reasons for modelling both taxa separately.

In Western Europe, *Quercus ilex* subsp. *ilex* is the most isolated evergreen oak among the four taxa. It grows mainly in Italy, reaching scarcely Spain through Southern France. The remaining taxa can be found more frequently as co-occurring in the Iberian Peninsula. In this area, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. coccifera* seem more able than *Q. suber* to withstand high xeric conditions (David et al. 2007; Peguero-Pina et al. 2009). As more eastwards rarer or absent become these oaks. *Quercus ilex* subsp. *ballota* does not reach Italy, whereas *Q. suber* can be found along the Tyrrhenian coast, the main islands and Apulia. *Quercus coccifera* occurs in scattered enclaves of few hectares in Sardinia, Sicily and Apulia. In Eastern Mediterranean, *Q. calliprinos* (Webb) Holmboe is found. This taxon is now considered a morphotype, belonging to the species *Q. coccifera* (Toumi & Lumaret 2010). In this area, specifically Turkey, it has been demonstrated the high water use efficiency of *Q. coccifera* in comparison with other shrub species (Ozturk et al. 2010). In general, environmental conditions of evergreen oak forests are characterised by mild

winters, seasonality (i.e. unequal precipitation throughout the year with drought period and high temperatures in summer) and low level in soil nutrients (Costa Tenorio et al. 2005). Nowadays, Mediterranean summers limit the forest growth whilst the forecasted climate shifts can accelerate leaf turnover in *Q. ilex* (Sabaté et al. 2002).

In the last decades, SDMs have been erected like an efficient technic for improving the knowledge on species potential distribution (Hidalgo et al. 2008; López-Tirado & Hidalgo 2014; Báez et al. 2016; Hemeri et al. 2016; López-Tirado & Hidalgo 2016a; Sadoti et al. 2016). Thus, they correlate the acknowledged current distribution of a given species with climatic conditions in the main; in other words, cartography of suitability is resulted from a list of explanatory variables (Mateo et al. 2011; Mellert et al. 2011). Oaks have also been studied separately in some specific areas of the Mediterranean Basin (Vessella & Schirone 2013; Vessella et al. 2015; Al-Qaddi et al. 2016; López-Tirado & Hidalgo 2016b, Modica et al. 2016); in some cases reaching the haplotype level (Simeone et al. 2009; Schirone et al. 2016; Simeone et al. 2016; Vitelli et al. 2017). Global Circulation Models (GCMs) are being improved each time. The availability of a wide range of algorithms, together with well-known species distributions and abiotic conditions, allows achieving more robust models. In fact, plant assemblages from single SDM are being addressed recently (Siles et al. 2010; Bonthoux et al. 2013; Pottier et al. 2013; Mikolajczak et al. 2015; Chai et al. 2016).

The present work aims: (i) to predict the suitability or potential distribution of four evergreen oaks in Western Europe; (ii) to forecast their potential distribution according to different future scenarios in a context of global change; (iii) to determine biogeographical interrelationships among the target species in the present and across the twenty-first century.

Materials and Methods

Study area and evergreen oaks occurrence

The study area spans Western Europe (Fig. 1). At the beginning a bigger area was thought to be encompassed, including North Africa, Middle East and Eastern Europe. Unfortunately, occurrence data was not at similar detail or it was incomplete throughout the desired study area; only scattered current distributions were found (cfr. Najvirt et al. 2008; Grozeva et al. 2014). Thus, a coherent criterion was taken, using a continuous study area with homogeneous available data. Four countries were studied: Portugal, Spain, France and Italy, nearest islands also included. From Portugal to Italy, warm areas close to the coast and high mountain ranges, such as the Baetic, the Pyrenees, the Alps or the Apennines, enable a heterogeneous orography. Thus, modelling approach can discriminate especially upward migration in forecasting.

FIGURE 1

Occurrence data was retrieved from each National Forest Inventory (NFI), excepting the scattered populations of *Q. coccifera* in Italy, which were taken from inventories of Sardinia, Sicily and Apulia. For each species, data was standardized at 30 arc-seconds resolution by means of ArcGIS 10 (ESRI, 2010), by counting as one the multiple points falling within a cell of 30 arc-seconds to avoid pseudo-replications. Finally, specific sets of unique points of presence were obtained as follows: *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* 49329 points, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* 212622 points, *Q. suber* 58132 points and *Q. coccifera* 26819 points.

Source of the explanatory variables

Nineteen climatic variables came from WorldClim 1.4 project at 30 arc-seconds resolution (Hijmans et al. 2005). Moreover, Emberger index (Q) was computed following the formula: $Q = 2000 \cdot P / M^2 - m^2$, where P is the annual rainfall, M^2 is the mean of the maximum temperatures of the warmest month, and m^2 is the mean of the minimum temperatures of the coldest month. Topographic variables were excluded because they remain invariable across time; hence they would

alter forecasting scenarios (López-Tirado & Hidalgo 2016a, 2016b). Table 1 shows the complete list of the used explanatory variables.

TABLE 1

Previous variables were downloaded from the interpolations of observed data between 1960 and 1990, which was considered the present period. Regarding future conditions, 13 GCMs calibrated for the Northern Hemisphere were taken into account: ACCESS1-0, BCC-CSM1-1, CCSM4, CNRM-CM5, GFDL-CM3, GISS-E2-R, HadGEM2-ES, INMCM4, IPSL-CM5A-LR, MIROC5, MPI-ESM-LR, MRI-CGCM3 and NorESM1-M. This information was retrieved from WorldClim 1.4 project, although the original data was available at the CMIP₅ (IPCC Fifth Assessment). The mean of all GCMs was calculated by means of ArcGIS 10 (ESRI, 2010) and one dataset was obtained to be modelled. This methodology was performed by two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs). They are concentration scenarios of greenhouse gases and pollutants resulting from human activities, adopted by the Fifth Assessment Report (IPCC 2014). Changes in land use with different socio-economic assumptions were also considered. From the four available RCPs, an intermediate and the most extreme scenarios were used. The first one achieved an impact of 4.5 W/m² by 2100, whereas the second one stated an increase of 8.5 W/m² also by 2100. Each RCP was surveyed in two periods: 2050 (average for 2041-2060) and 2070 (average for 2061-2080). To sum up, four different scenarios (RCP 4.5 2050, RCP 4.5 2070, RCP 8.5 2050 and RCP 8.5 2070) were forecasted for each target taxa.

Models' performance and validation

The development of the models was carried out by means of three algorithms, each one belonging to a different statistical technique (table 2). In the case of LR, the dependent variable (occurrence) was considered as binary; absence data was created in ArcGIS 10 (ESRI, 2010) by

create random points tool. Then, in SPSS statistics 20 software, the *Forward conditional method* was applied, i.e. the most significant variables were chosen in the first steps, whereas lesser ones were rejected. The output result led to a β value that was implemented in the binary logistic regression formula and the probability of potential occurrence was finally obtained by taxon (ranging from 0 to 1) for the present period. For MaxEnt and EnvDis pseudo-absence points were randomly generated by their respective programs. In both cases, training and testing data percentages were set to 75% and 25%, respectively. An ASCII raster at 30 arc-seconds resolution was resulted with the suitability of the evergreen oaks ranging from 0 to 100 for MaxEnt and from 0 to 1 for EnvDis. Then, output results from LR and EnvDis were rescaled at the interval from 0 to 100, thus standardizing the three algorithms.

TABLE 2

The validation method was the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, calculating the Area Under the Curve (AUC). It is a powerful tool to measure the quality of a probabilistic classifier (Ben-David 2008; Fawcett 2006; Fielding & Bell 1997; Vuk & Curk 2006). AUC was also used to build a weighted average consensus map among the algorithms with the following formula (Vessella et al. 2015):

$$X_{pond} = \frac{\sum_n^{i=1} z_i AUC_i}{\sum_n^{i=1} AUC_i}$$

where z is the probability of the potential occurrence of the cell of the i -model multiplied by its AUC score. Consensus maps for the present time, together with the future explanatory variables, were the base for building the future scenarios maps, which were reclassified in ten intervals by means of ArcGIS 10 (ESRI, 2010).

Assessing the potentiality among evergreen oaks

Probability score of all evergreen oaks was transferred from raster file to vector point shapefile into ArcGIS 10 (ESRI, 2010). The latter was managed with the *selection by attributes* tool. Thus, specific records were selected according to the dominance among them. Cells which had a value under 50 for all the studied taxa were discarded due to the low potentiality of occurrence. Dominance was considered when a given oak had a score over 20 with respect to the others. Codominance was also discriminated encompassing two, three or all the evergreen oaks respectively, taking into account an occurrence under 20 unities (Mikolajczak et al. 2015). A field from the associated database of the shapefile recorded each selected group and a final map was built. This methodology was repeated for the future scenarios.

Results

Species distribution models by taxa

The performance of the three algorithms separately led to different degrees of restriction. MaxEnt was the most restrictive algorithm, LR showed an intermediate approach and EnvDis computed a wider potential area for the studied taxa. The consensus map of evergreen oaks is shown as electronic appendices as follows: (i) EA1a and EA1b for *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* in the present period and future scenarios respectively; (ii) EA2a and EA2b for *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* in the present period and future scenarios respectively; (iii) EA3a and EA3b for *Q. suber* in the present period and future scenarios respectively; and (iv) EA4a and EA4b for *Q. coccifera* in the present period and future scenarios respectively. The predicted surface of the consensus map for values over 50 % of probability to each species is shown in table 3. All the evergreen oaks showed a spread potential area for the present period with respect to the current distribution. At the same time, present period resulted with lower potential distribution in comparison with the future scenarios. Among the latter, RCP4.5 in 2050 is the scenario with lower predicted surface, whereas RCP 8.5 in 2070 displays the highest one, excepting RCP 4.5 in 2070 for *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex*.

TABLE 3

Quercus ilex subsp. *ilex* at the present period (EA1a) encompasses the main stands in the Italian Peninsula and the nearest islands, especially in Sardinia. Part of the Southern French coast and Northern Levantine coast of Spain are also suitable patches for the occurrence of this taxon. The Cantabrian coast and the Balearic Islands show quite good probability of occurrence, especially in Northern Mallorca, called *Sierra de Tramontana*, where this oak reaches higher probability at higher elevation with respect to the rest of the island. *Quercus ilex* subsp. *ilex* undergoes the highest shift in the future (see EA1b). This is especially remarkable in France and Portugal; both countries are partially occupied by the suitability of this taxon according to our results. Also this probability of occurrence is increased in Italy and Northern Spain. High range mountains such as the Alps or the Pyrenees, together with Southern Portugal, inland Spain, Northeastern France and *Pianura Padana* in Italy remain with low potential distribution.

Good suitability of *Quercus ilex* subsp. *ballota* (over 50 %) is located exclusively in the Iberian Peninsula at the present period. Exceptions are found around the coastline, Northwestern Iberian Peninsula, the Pyrenees and the Ebro Depression (EA2a). Forecasting states suitable areas outside the Iberian Peninsula (EA2b). Southern half of France (especially in the coast) and some patches in the Tyrrhenian and the Adriatic coast of Italy become suitable, especially in the latter (Apulia region). South of Sardinia and Western Sicily (Southern exposure of Etna volcano) are worth of mention as well. Finally, it is interesting how Balearic Islands show lesser suitability for this subspecies than for *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex*.

The potential distribution of *Q. suber* is concentrated in Southwestern Iberian Peninsula at the present period (EA3a). Unlike *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*, this species reaches the coastline in this area. Some isolated spots can be detected along the coast from Southern Spain to Central Italy. The most important is located in the Catalonian coast. Regarding islands, north half of Sardinia and South coast of Sicily show also good suitability. In the predicted future scenarios (EA3b), cork oak

is the species with lesser upward latitudinal migration, reaching France (only a small suitable area in the Atlantic coast). In contrast, a strong spread in the Italian Peninsula and all the islands (Balearic Islands, Corse, Sardinia and Sicily) can be noticed. The coast between Spain and Italy is also increased in potentiality. On the other hand, inland Spain and France, as well as high mountains are not reached by this species. It can be observed how the highest summits of the Baetic Range are surrounded, showing null occurrence probability.

Quercus coccifera exhibits a similar potential distribution in the present period (EA4a) in comparison with *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*, although shows complementarity with the latter. The main potential area is wider while further East. For instance, Ebro Depression fits better to this species than to *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*. Outside Iberian Peninsula, only the Mediterranean French coast and slightly Sardinia, Sicily and Apulia region (Italy) are suitable patches for *Q. coccifera*. Forecasting (EA4b) shows a general spread in the abovementioned zones. It is interesting how the potential area in the future run to the Atlantic environment, i.e. closer to Portugal as well as the appearance of suitability in Western France. The Mediterranean area is also incremented, especially noticeable in South of France and the Balearic Islands.

Table 4 displays the AUC values to each taxa and algorithm. They state a good validation of the models with high accuracy.

TABLE 4

Dominance and codominance among evergreen oaks

Predicted surface of dominance, codominance and absence (grids under 50 for all the taxa) is shown in table 5. According to our results, absence grids are lesser in the forecasted scenarios. Dominance of three out of four evergreen oaks undergoes a decrease in the future scenarios. Only *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* raises its dominance, partially due to the huge spread in France. That generalised surface loss is balanced and gained by codominance among the taxa. The most remarkable case is

among *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* and *Q. coccifera*, being increased from 0.45% in the present period to 12.09-17.27% in the future scenarios.

TABLE 5

Figure 2a exposes different dominances and codominances among evergreen oaks. Dominance of *Quercus suber* is located mainly in Portugal and a belt along the South Atlantic coast of Spain. It is especially surrounded by codominance with *Quercus coccifera* and *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*. The former controls Eastern Spain (Levantine area and Ebro Depression) and some areas in the South of France; the latter dominates Western Spain mainly. On the other hand, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* is the most present taxa in the Italian Peninsula, Corse, Sardinia, Sicily and some littoral places in Spain. Interesting codominances are also as follows: (i) *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. coccifera*, which spans a large extent in Central Spain; (ii) *Q. suber*, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. coccifera* in Southwest Spain; (iii) *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* and *Q. coccifera* in the South coast of France, Apulia region (Italy), a patch at the Levantine coast of Spain and Central Mallorca; and (iv) *Q. suber* and *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* in some areas of Corse and Italy, as well as Menorca.

FIGURE 2a

The forecasted scenarios (Fig. 2b) state several results. The main dominant area to *Q. suber* remains in Central-South Portugal. Its previous dominance in Northern Portugal is displaced by codominance between *Q. suber*, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* and *Q. coccifera*. The scattered codominance between *Q. suber* and *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* in the present period is grouped in a small spot in South-western Iberian Peninsula. Dominance of *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. coccifera* is occupied by their own codominance. On the other hand, dominance of *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* rises due to the colonisation of Western France. Nevertheless, in Italy it undergoes a decreasing, harmed by the

presence of *Q. suber* (codominance between them). Most of France is taken by the occurrence of three codominances very scarce in the present period: (i) *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* and *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*; (ii) *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex*, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. coccifera*; and (iii) codominance among the four taxa. These new suitable areas are especially important in RCP 8.5 (2070). High mountain, together with some inland French areas, *Pianura Padana* (Northern Italy) and Galician coastal territory remain like not potentially settled by any evergreen oak.

FIGURE 2b

Discussion

Robustness of the work

The potential distribution in the present as well as along the twenty-first century for four evergreen oaks has been addressed in Western Europe. The mean of 13 GCMs calibrated for the Northern Hemisphere and three algorithms with different performance were used. MaxEnt resulted lower AUC values than LR and EnvDis (see table 4). In any case, AUC results confirm a very good validation of the models according to Swets (1988) as follows: 0.5–0.7 as low accuracy; 0.7–0.9 as potentially useful; and >0.9 as high accuracy. Encompassing the abovementioned working process, together with the creation of the consensus maps, this study has taken high accurate robustness. Moreover, this paper goes beyond single SDMs. Dominance and codominance of the target taxa were analysed and assessed with novel and remarkable results.

Ecology and modelling of evergreen oaks

A large difference is underlined in the predicted surface between present and future scenarios. Among the latter, RCP 8.5 in 2070 shows the highest predicted surface excepting *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex*. Thus, higher emissions higher potentiality, stating that global warming could allow a theoretical spread of evergreen oaks. *Quercus suber* is the evergreen oak with lower predicted

surface (table 3). It is a calcifuge species with more specific requirements than the others, such as acid soils (Tutin et al. 1993) –although rarely can grow in hard limestones (Valle, 2004)- and temperate areas; having its optimal in South-western Iberian Peninsula. In general, *Q. suber* and *Q. coccifera* can be considered more thermophilous than other taxa studied here. *Quercus ilex* shows a wide ecological plasticity, in some cases bearing harsh xeric conditions (Petroselli et al. 2013; López-Tirado & Hidalgo 2016b). In an aridity-humidity range, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. coccifera* endure better aridity than the other species. For instance, *Q. coccifera* can regulate water loss depending on Mediterranean or temperate conditions (Peguero-Pina et al. 2015). On the other hand, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* is the one which needs more humidity or water availability, remaining *Q. suber* in an intermediate position. This is consistent with the most severe poleward migration by *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex*, mainly covering Western France in the future scenarios (cfr. electronic appendices). Far from its current distribution, in Central Portugal a patch became suitable for *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex*; this is maybe due to the influence of the Atlantic Ocean, an adaptive condition for this oak (Costa Tenorio et al. 2005; Petroselli et al. 2013). Regarding *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. coccifera*, a similar distribution can be noticed, although a gradient is detected in the Iberian Peninsula. *Quercus ilex* subsp. *ballota* rules in the Central-western zone, whereas *Q. coccifera* does it in Central-eastern part (Villar-Salvador et al. 2013). The former can resist very low temperatures, surviving up to -24°C for short periods in winter (Knopf 2002). Thus, it can grow in the central plateau inland Spain, especially like shrub layer. *Quercus ilex* is indifferent to the substrate (Musarella et al. 2012), whilst *Q. coccifera* can be more competitive in basic soils as well as lower and warmer areas (López González 2007), and consequently more frequent at the Levantine Iberian Peninsula –e.g. Ebro Depression–.

Dominance and codominance interrelationships of evergreen oaks

Occurrence and co-occurrence of the target taxa pointed out that the study area would have lesser absence grids in the future than in the present. Thus, the poleward migration trend is noticed

from meridional species. Nevertheless, at the distribution edge in Southern areas, species could persist suggesting adaptation to stressful environments (García-Nogales et al. 2016). Co-occurrence of *Q. suber*, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. coccifera* will be increased along the twenty-first century. This trend has already been revealed by mixed forests along the time (Moreno-Fernández et al. 2016). Only *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* will undergo an increasing dominance. This is consistent with its more isolated current distribution with respect to the other evergreen oaks (Tutin et al. 1993). Moreover, this taxon reaches Western France, a territory not really suitable for the other evergreen oaks.

The trio in the Iberian Peninsula is particularly interesting. Codominance among the three species or between two of them are slightly higher in the future scenarios, but *Q. suber* and *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* which is lower. These three oaks co-occur in South-western Spain, surrounded by *Q. suber* at the West (Portugal) and by *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. coccifera* at the East (Central Spain). Thus, addressed by the specific requirements of the species, it is a patent gradient between *Q. suber* and *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*. On the other hand, *Quercus coccifera* is mainly a shrub in the Iberian Peninsula (do Amaral Franco 1990; López González 2007), which is closer to *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*, belonging to the understory in climax stands. Hybridisations between *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. coccifera* (*Quercus x agrifolia* Batt.) are frequent (Rubio de Casas et al. 2007; Ortego & Bonal 2010). Codominance by these taxa is the most spread in Spain, thus hybrids between them could be increased along the twenty-first century. As a consequence of increasing predicted surface in codominances, *Q. suber*, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. coccifera* undergo a decrease in the single dominances. Mixed forests are not rare in the Iberian Peninsula, despite human management favoured a given species (Cañellas et al., 2000; Sánchez-Palomares et al., 2008). In fact, *Q. suber* and *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* forests share a wide range of phytosociological communities along the succession to the climax. Some of them are: *Asparago albi-Rhamnetum oleoidis* subass. *rhamnetosum oleoidis*, *Genisto hirsutae-Cistetum ladaniferi*, *Scillo maritimae-Lavanduletum*

sampaiana, *Trifolium cherleri-Taeniatheretum capitis-medusae*, *Bromo tectori-Stipetum capensis*, etc. (Valle 2004; Muñoz Álvarez 2010).

Continental France only shows suitable areas for evergreen oaks in the Mediterranean coast at the present period. The effect of fire has been studied for *Q. coccifera* in this area (Trabaud 2009). The latter together with *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* are the most frequent taxa; especially their co-occurrence. This codominance is enriched with *Q. suber* in two patches, the bigger in Var department. The forecasted scenarios considerably enlarge the potential distribution of evergreen oaks in this country. The most noticeable trait is the change of the South coast to a codominance of all the oaks studied here. This codominance is poorer the further inland. The first species that disappear from this co-existence is *Q. suber* –species which does not withstand very low temperatures (Costa Tenorio 2005)–, followed by *Q. coccifera* in the inner areas. Again it is manifested the thermophilic behaviour of the latter, in contrast with an evident ecological plasticity of *Q. ilex*. In fact, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* shows good photosystem II efficiency during summer, due to the presence of trichomes in the adaxial leaf surface as opposed to *Q. coccifera* (Morales et al. 2002). Some spots of *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* and *Q. coccifera* are predicted at the boundary with the huge dominance of *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* in Western France.

As the previous countries, the Italian Peninsula experiences an increment of codominance in the forecasted scenarios. For the present, almost all continental Italy (excepting North Italy and high mountains in the rest) is occupied by *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex*. Codominance between the latter and *Q. coccifera* is predicted in a lower way, especially in Apulia region, place in which exist some stands of this shrub (Sabato 1973; Bianco & Schirone 1985). *Quercus suber* occurrence remain testimonial, always co-occurring with *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* and *Q. coccifera*. All the taxa would find codominance in some scattered sites along the Tyrrhenian and the Adriatic seas in the future scenarios. *Quercus suber* presence becomes more evident –always in codominance- and it is also interesting the emergence of a spot codominated by *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and *Q. coccifera* near *Promontorio del Gargano*.

Regarding islands, only *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* –and slightly *Q. suber*– shows single dominance. In the forecasted scenarios, codominances become greater and an upward migration in elevation is noticed by *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* in Etna volcano (Sicily).

Conclusions

Ecosystems conservation must be a prior objective for scientists in this forecasted changing century. It has been stated how *Q. ilex* growth was only correlated with water availability in the twentieth century; nevertheless, this growth was shortened in the present century because of consistent drought during summer (Lempereur et al. 2016; Mancilla-Leytón et al. 2016). The upcoming frequency of extreme droughts will be a challenge for forests recovering (Barbeta & Peñuelas 2016). The predicted warming can have a strong impact on the productivity of Mediterranean forests (Boisvenue & Running, 2006; Helman et al. 2017). Preservation of older, larger and well-connected *Q. ilex* stands in agricultural areas is essential for specialist insects and biodiversity in general (Ruiz-Carbayo et al. 2016). This is also important in forest plantations, in which finding a balance between productivity and biodiversity is a key goal in management (Barsoum et al. 2016). *Quercus suber* decline can alter soil respiration and nutrients having effects in other successional forest species and implying vegetation shifts (Ávila et al. 2016; Ibáñez et al 2016). Thus, the implementation of SDMs can clarify the trends and dynamics of the species. According to our results, evergreen oaks could be benefited by global change, making up larger mixed forests than the current ones. These results are highly useful for afforestation and restoration programmes, aiming to manage field areas in the upcoming climatic change conditions.

Acknowledgements

References

- Acácio, V., Dias, F.S., Catry, F.X., Rocha, M & Moreira, F. 2016. Landscape dynamics in Mediterranean oak forests under global change: understanding the role of anthropogenic and environmental drivers across forest types. *Global Change Biology*. doi: 10.1111/gcb.13487.
- Al-Qaddi, N., Vessella, F., Stephan, J., Al-Eisawi, D. & Schirone, B. 2016. Current and future suitability areas of kermes oak (*Quercus coccifera* L.) in the Levant under climate change. *Regional Environmental Change*. doi: 10.1007/s10113-016-0987-2.
- Alejano, R., Vázquez-Piqué, J., Carevic, F. & Fernández, M. 2011. Do ecological and silvicultural factors influence acorn mass in Holm-oak (southwestern Spain)? *Agroforestry Systems* 83: 25–39.
- Ávila, J.M., Gallardo, A., Ibáñez, B. & Gómez-Aparicio, L. 2016. *Quercus suber* dieback alters soil respiration and nutrient availability in Mediterranean forests. *Journal of Ecology*. doi: 10.1111/1365-2745.12618.
- Báez, S., Jaramillo, L., Cuesta, F. & Donoso, D.A. 2016. Effects of climate change on Andean biodiversity: a synthesis of studies published until 2015. *Neotropical Biodiversity* 2: 181–194. doi: 10.1080/23766808.2016.1248710.
- Barbeta, A. & Peñuelas, J. 2016. Sequence of plant responses to droughts of different timescales: lessons from holm oak (*Quercus ilex*) forests. *Plant Ecology & Diversity*. doi: 10.1080/17550874.2016.1212288.
- Barsoum, N., Coote, L., Eycott, A.E., Fuller, L, Kiewitt, A. & Davies, R.G. 2016. Diversity, functional structure and functional redundancy of woodland plant communities: How do mixed tree species plantations compare with monocultures? *Forest Ecology and Management* 382: 244–256.
- Ben-David, A. 2008. About the relationship between ROC curves and Cohen's kappa. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* 21: 874–882.
- Bianco, P. & Schirone, B. 1985. On *Quercus coccifera* L. s.l.: Variation in Reproductive Phenology. *Taxon* 34: 436-439.
- Boisvenue, C. & Running, S.W. 2006. Impacts of climate change on natural forest productivity – evidence since the middle of the 20th century. *Global Change Biology* 12: 862–882.
- Cañellas, I., García, F.M. & Montero, G. 2000. Silviculture and dynamics of *Pinus sylvestris* stands in Spain. *Investigación Agraria. Sistemas y Recursos Forestales. Fuera de serie*: 233–253.
- Chai, Z., Fan, D. & Wang, D. 2016. Environmental Factors and Underlying Mechanisms of Tree Community Assemblages of Pine-oak Mixed Forests in the Qinling Mountains, China. *Journal of Plant Biology* 59: 357-367.
- Costa Tenorio, M., Morla Juaristi, C. & Sainz Ollero, H. 2005. Los Bosques Ibéricos. Una interpretación geobotánica. Editorial Planeta, Barcelona.
- David, T.S., Henriques, M.O., Kurz-Besson, C., Nunes, J., Valente, F., Vaz, M., Pereira, J.S., Siegwolf, R., Chaves, M.M., Gazarini, L.C. & David, J.S. 2007. Water-use strategies in two

co-occurring Mediterranean evergreen oaks: surviving the summer drought. *Tree Physiology* 27: 793-803.

- de Rigo, D. & Caudullo, G. 2016. *Quercus ilex* in Europe: distribution, habitat, usage and threats. In: San-Miguel-Ayanz, J., de Rigo, D., Caudullo, G., Durrant, T.H. & Mauri, A. (eds.) *European Atlas of Forest Tree Species*. Publication Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- Dirzo, R. & Raven, P.H. 2003. Global state of biodiversity and loss. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources* 28: 137-167. doi:10.1146/annurev.energy.28.050302.105532
- do Amaral Franco, J. 1990. *Quercus* L. *Flora Iberica*, vol II. CSIC, Madrid, pp 15–36.
- Fawcett, T. 2006. An introduction to ROC analysis. *Pattern Recognition Letters* 27: 861–874.
- Fielding, A.H. & Bell, J.F. 1997. A review of methods for the assessment of prediction errors in conservation presence/absence models. *Environmental Conservation* 24: 38–49.
- García-Nogales, A., Linares, J.C., Laureano, R.G., Seco, J. & Merino, J. 2016. Range-wide variation in life-history phenotypes: Spatiotemporal plasticity across the latitudinal gradient of the evergreen oak *Quercus ilex* *Journal of Biogeography*. doi: 10.1111/jbi.12849.
- Godinho, S., Gil, A., Guiomar, N., Costa M.J. & Neves, N. 2016. Assessing the role of Mediterranean evergreen oaks canopy cover in land surface albedo and temperature using a remote sensing-based approach. *Applied Geography* 74: 84-94.
- Grozeva, N., Dohchev, D., Gerdzhikova, M., Tsutsov, K., Todorova, M., Panayotova, G. & Getova, N. 2014. New data for protected plants of Sinite Kamani Natural Park Sliven. *Trakia Journal of Sciences* 1: 13-20.
- Helman, D., Osem, Y., Yakir, D. & Lensky, I.M. 2017. Relationships between climate, topography, water use and productivity in two key Mediterranean forest types with different water-use strategies. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 232: 319-330.
- Hemery, L.G., Marion, S.R., Romsos, C.G., Kurapov, A.L. & Henkel, S.K. 2016. Ecological niche and species distribution modelling of sea stars along the Pacific Northwest continental shelf. *Diversity and Distributions* 22: 1314-1327.
- Hidalgo, P.J., Marín, J.M., Quijada, J., Moreira, J.M. 2008. A spatial distribution model of cork-oak (*Quercus suber*) in southwestern Spain: a suitable tool for reforestation. *Forest Ecology and Management* 255: 25–34.
- Hijmans, R.J., Cameron, S.E., Parra, J.L., Jones, P.G. & Jarvis, A. 2005. Very high resolution interpolated climate surfaces for global land areas. *International Journal of Climatology* 25: 1965-1978.
- Ibáñez, B., Gómez-Aparicio, L., Ávila, J.M., Pérez-Ramos, I.M. & Marañón, T. 2016. Effects of *Quercus suber* Decline on Woody Plant Regeneration: Potential Implications for Successional Dynamics in Mediterranean Forests. *Ecosystems*. doi: 10.1007/s10021-016-0044-5.

- IPCC 2014. Climate Change 2014: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. I.P.C.C., Geneva (Switzerland)
- Jacobs, D.F., Oliet, J.A., Aronson, J., Bolte, A., Bullock, J.M., Donoso, P.J., Landhäuser, S.M., Madsen, P., Peng, S., Rey-Benayas, J.M. & Weber, J.C. 2015. Restoring forests: What constitutes success in the twenty-first century? *New Forests* 46: 601-614.
- Knopf, H.E. 2002. Enzyklopädie der Holzgewächse: Handbuch und Atlas der Dendrologie. Roloff, A., Weisgerber, H., Lang, U.M., Stimm, B. & Schütt, P. (eds.). Wiley-Vch Verlag, Weinheim.
- Leakey, R.E. & Lewin, R. 1996. The Sixth Extinction: Patterns of Life and the Future of Humankind. Anchor Books.
- Lebreton, P., Barbero, M. & Quezel, P. 2001. Morphometric and biochemical contributions to the structuration and systematics of the Holm oak *Quercus ilex* L. specific complex. *Acta Botanica Gallica* 148: 289-317.
- Lempereur, M., Limousin, J.M., Guibal, F., Ourcival, J.M., Rambal, S., Ruffault, J. & Mouillot, F. 2016. Recent climate hiatus revealed dual control by temperature and drought on the stem growth of Mediterranean *Quercus ilex*. *Global Change Biology*. doi: 10.1111/gcb.13495.
- López de Heredia, U., Jimenez, P., Collada, C., Simeone, M.C., Bellarosa, R., Schirone, B., Cervera, M.T. & Gil, L. 2007. Multi-marker phylogeny of three evergreen oaks reveals vicariant patterns in the Western Mediterranean. *Taxon* 56: 1209-1220.
- López González, G.A. 2007. *Guía de los árboles y arbustos de la Península Ibérica y Baleares*, 3ª edición. Ediciones Mundi-Prensa, Madrid
- López Quintanilla, J. (coord.) 2013. *Los pinsapares en Andalucía (Abies pinsapo Boiss.) Conservación y sostenibilidad en el siglo XXI*, 576 pp. Servicio de publicaciones Universidad de Córdoba, Córdoba.
- López-Tirado, J. & Hidalgo, P.J. 2014. A high resolution predictive model for relict trees in the Mediterranean-mountain forests (*Pinus sylvestris* L., *P. nigra* Arnold and *Abies pinsapo* Boiss.) from the south of Spain: A reliable management tool for reforestation. *Forest Ecology and Management* 330: 105-114.
- López-Tirado, J. & Hidalgo, P.J. 2016a. Ecological niche modelling of three Mediterranean pine species in the south of Spain: a tool for afforestation/reforestation programs in the twenty-first century. *New Forests* 47: 411-429.
- López-Tirado, J. & Hidalgo, P.J. 2016b. Predictive modelling of climax oak trees in southern Spain: Insights in a scenario of global change. *Plant Ecology* 217: 451-463.
- Lumaret, R., Mir, C., Michaud, H. & Raynal, V. 2002. Phylogeographical variation of chloroplast DNA in holm oak (*Quercus ilex* L.). *Molecular Ecology* 11: 2327-2336.
- Mancilla-Leytón, J.M., Leiva, M.J. & Martín Vicente, A. 2016. Soil compaction and water availability affect growth and survival of *Quercus ilex* subsp. *ballota* seedlings under different light environments. *New Forests*. doi: 10.1007/s11056-016-9534-8

- Marañón, T., Pugnaire, F.I. & Callaway, R.M. 2009. Mediterranean-climate oak savannas: the interplay between abiotic environment and species interactions. *Web Ecology* 9: 30–43.
- Mateo, R.G., Felicísimo, A.M. & Muñoz, J. 2011. Modelos de distribución de especies: Una revisión sintética. *Revista Chilena de Historia Natural* 84: 217–240.
- Matesanz, S. & Valladares, F. 2014. Ecological and evolutionary responses of Mediterranean plants to global change. *Environmental and Experimental Botany* 103: 53–67.
- Mellert, K.H., Fensterer, V., Küchenhoff, H., Reger, B., Kölling, C., Klemmt, H.J. & Ewald, J. 2011. Hypothesis-driven species distribution models for tree species in the Bavarian Alps. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 22: 635–646.
- Michaud, H., Toumi, L., Lumaret, R., Li, T.X., Romane, F. & Di Giusto, F. 1995. Effect of geographical discontinuity on genetic variation in *Quercus ilex* L. (holm oak). Evidence from enzyme polymorphism. *Heredity* 74: 590–606.
- Mikolajczak, A., Marechal, D., Sanz, T., Iseninann, M., Thierion, V. & Luque, S. 2015. Modelling spatial distributions of alpine vegetation: A graph theory approach to delineate ecologically-consistent species assemblages. *Ecological Informatics* 30: 196–202.
- Modica, G., Solano, F., Merlino, A., Di Fazio, S., Barreca, F., Lauradi, L. & Fichera C.R. 2016. Using Landsat 8 imagery in detecting cork oak (*Quercus suber* L.) woodlands: a case study in Calabria (Italy). *Journal of Agricultural Engineering* 47: 205–215.
- Moles, M.A. et al. 2014. Which is a better predictor of plant traits: Temperature or precipitation? *Journal of Vegetation Science* 25: 1167–1180.
- Morales, F., Abadía, A., Abadía, J., Montserrat, G. & Gil Pelegrín, E. 2002. Trichomes and photosynthetic pigment composition changes: Responses of *Quercus ilex* subsp. *ballota* (Desf.) Samp. and *Quercus coccifera* L. to Mediterranean stress conditions. *Trees* 16: 504–510.
- Moreno-Fernández, D., Hernández, L., Sánchez-González, M., Cañellas, I. & Montes, F. 2016. Space–time modeling of changes in the abundance and distribution of tree species. *Forest Ecology and Management* 372: 206–216.
- Muñoz Álvarez, J.M. 2010. Vegetación de la Reserva de la Biosfera y de los Espacios Naturales de Sierra Morena. Consejería de Medio Ambiente, Junta de Andalucía, Córdoba, Spain
- Musarella, C.M., Spampinato, G., Cano-Ortiz, A., Piñar Fuentes, J.C., Pinto Gomes, C.J. & Cano, E. 2010. Ecological and phytosociological comparison between *Quercus ilex* L. subsp. *ilex* of southern Italy and *Q. rotundifolia* Lam. of southern Iberian Peninsula. 47th Congress of the Italian Society for Vegetation Science. Opportunities and Challenges for Vegetation Science in a Changing World. Perugia, Italy.
- Najvirt, Z., Milcevic, A. & Mestrovic, S. 2008. Area of the Kermes oak (*Quercus coccifera* L.) on the western part of peninsula Peljesac. *Sumarski List* 132: 253–258.
- Ortego, J. & Bonal, R. 2010. Natural hybridisation between kermes (*Quercus coccifera* L.) and holm oaks (*Q. ilex* L.) revealed by microsatellite markers. *Planta Biology* 12: 234–238.

- Ozturk, M., Dogan, Y., Sakcali, M.S., Doulis, A. & Karam, F. 2010. Ecophysiological responses of some maquis (*Ceratonia siliqua* L., *Olea oleaster* Hoffm. & Link, *Pistacia lentiscus* and *Quercus coccifera* L.) plant species to drought in the east Mediterranean ecosystem. *Journal of Environmental Biology* 31: 233-245.
- Peguero-Pina, J.J., Sancho-Knapik, D., Morales, F., Flexas, J. & Gil-Pelegrín, E. 2009. Differential photosynthetic performance and photoprotection mechanisms of three Mediterranean evergreen oaks under severe drought stress. *Functional Plant Biology* 36: 453-462.
- Peguero-Pina, J.J., Sancho-Knapik, D., Barron, E., Camarero, J.J., Vilagrosa, A. & Gil-Pelegrin, E. 2014. Morphological and physiological divergences within *Quercus ilex* support the existence of different ecotypes depending on climatic dryness. *Annals of Botany* 114: 301-313.
- Peguero-Pina, J.J., Sisó, S., Fernández-Marín, B., Flexas, J., Galmes, J., García-Plazaola, J.I., Niinemets, U., Sancho-Knapik, D. & Gil-Pelegrin, E. 2016. Leaf functional plasticity decreases the water consumption without further consequences for carbon uptake in *Quercus coccifera* L. under Mediterranean conditions. *Tree physiology* 36: 356-367.
- Petroselli, A., Vessella, F., Cavagnuolo, L., Piovesan, G. & Schirone, B. 2013. Ecological behavior of *Quercus suber* and *Quercus ilex* inferred by topographic wetness index (TWI). *Trees - Structure and Function* 27: 1201-1215.
- Rafii, Z.A., Zavarin, E. & Pelleau, Y. 1991. Chemosystematic differentiation of *Quercus ilex* and *Q. rotundifolia* based on acorn fatty acids. *Biochemical Systematics and Ecology* 19: 163-166.
- Regnery, B., Paillet, Y., Couvet, D. & Kerbiriou, C. 2013. Which factors influence the occurrence and density of tree microhabitats in Mediterranean oak forests? *Forest Ecology and Management* 295: 118-125.
- Reyes-López, J., Ruiz, N. & Fernández-Haeger, J. 2003. Community structure of ground-ants: the role of single trees in a Mediterranean pastureland. *Acta Oecologica* 24: 195-202.
- Rubio de Casas, R., Cano, E., Balaguer, L., Pérez-Corona, M.E., Manrique, E., García-Verdugo, C. & Vargas, P. 2007. Taxonomic identity of *Quercus coccifera* L. in the Iberian Peninsula is maintained in spite of widespread hybridisation, as revealed by morphological, ISSR and ITS sequence data. *Flora - Morphology Distribution Functional Ecology of Plants* 202: 488-499.
- Ruiz, N., García, G., Reyes, J. 1999. Uso de la encina (*Quercus ilex* spp. *ballota*) por la hormiga *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) como refugio ante medios desfavorables. *Boln. Asoc. esp. Ent.* 23: 115-125.
- Ruiz-Carbayo, H., Bonal, R., Espelta, J.M., Hernández, M. & Pino, J. 2016. Community assembly in time and space: The case of Lepidoptera in a *Quercus ilex* L. savannah-like landscape. *Insect Conservation and Diversity*. doi: 10.1111/icad.12184.
- Sabaté, S., Gracia, C.A. & Sanchez, A. 2002. Likely effects of climate change on growth of *Quercus ilex*, *Pinus halepensis*, *Pinus pinaster*, *Pinus sylvestris* and *Fagus sylvatica* forests in the Mediterranean region. *Forest Ecology and Management* 162: 23-37.

- Sabato, S. 1973. Considerazioni sul significato fitogeografico ed ecologico di « quercus coccifera » l. s.l. nel salento (puglia). *Webbia* 27: 517-549.
- Sadaka-Laulan, N. & Ponge, J.F. 2000. Comparative leaf decomposition within the holm oak complex. *European Journal of Soil Biology* 36: 91-95.
- Sadoti, G., Albright, T.P. & Johnson, K. 2016. Applying dynamic species distribution modelling to lek-mating species. *Journal of Biogeography*. doi:10.1111/jbi.12886.
- Sánchez-Palomares, O., Roig, S., del Río, M., Rubio, A. & Gandullo, J. 2008. *Las estaciones ecológicas actuales y potenciales de los rebollares españoles*. Monografías INIA: Serie forestal nº. 17, Madrid.
- Schirone, B., Radoglou, K. & Vessella, F. 2016. Conservation and restoration strategies to preserve the variability of cork oak *Quercus suber* — a Mediterranean forest species — under global warming. *Climate Research*. doi: 10.3354/cr01440.
- Simeone, M.C., Grimm, G.W., Papini, A., Vessella, F., Cardoni, S., Tordoni, E., Piredda, R., Franc, A. & Denk, T. 2016. Plastome data reveal multiple geographic origins of *Quercus* Group Ilex. PeerJ. doi: 10.7717/peerj.1897.
- Simeone, M.C., Papini, A., Vessella, F., Bellarosa, R., Spada, F. & Schirone, B. 2009. Multiple genome relationships and a complex biogeographic history in the eastern range of *Quercus suber* L. (Fagaceae) implied by nuclear and chloroplast DNA variation. *Caryologia* 62: 236-252.
- Swets, J.A. 1988. Measuring the accuracy of diagnostic systems. *Science* 240: 1285–1293.
- Thuiller, W., Lavergne, S., Roquet, C., Boulangeat, I., Lafourcade, B., Araújo, M.B. 2011. Consequences of climate change on the tree of life in Europe. *Nature* 470 (7335): 531-534. doi:10.1038/nature09705.
- Toumi, L. & Lumaret, R. 2010. Genetic variation and evolutionary history of holly oak: A circum-Mediterranean species-complex [*Quercus coccifera* L./*Q. calliprinos* (Webb) Holmboe, Fagaceae]. *Plant Systematics and Evolution* 290: 159-171.
- Trabaud, L. 2009. Fire regimes and phytomass growth dynamics in a *Quercus coccifera* garrigue. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 2: 307-314.
- Tutin, T.G., Burges, N.A., Chater, A.O., Edmondson, J.R., Heywood, V.H., Moore, D.M., Valentine, D.H., Walters, S.M. & Webb, D.A. 1993. *Flora Europaea*, vol. 1 (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Urbieto, I.R., Zavala, M.A. & Marañón, T. 2008. Human and non-human determinants of forest composition in southern Spain: evidence of shifts towards cork oak dominance as a result of management over the past century. *Journal of Biogeography* 35: 1688-1700.
- Valle, F. (coord.) 2004. *Modelos de restauración forestal*. Consejería de Medio Ambiente, Junta de Andalucía, Sevilla, Spain.
- Vericat, P., Piqué, M. & Serrada, R. 2012. *Gestión adaptativa al cambio global en masas de Quercus mediterráneas*. Centre Tecnològic Forestal de Catalunya, Lleida.

- Vessella, F. & Schirone, B. 2013. Predicting potential distribution of *Quercus suber* in Italy based on ecological niche models: Conservation insights and reforestation involvements. *Forest Ecology and Management* 304: 150-161. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2013.05.006.
- Vessella, F., Simeone, M.C. & Schirone, B. 2015. *Quercus suber* range dynamics by ecological niche modelling: from the Last Interglacial to present time. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 119: 85-93.
- Villar-Salvador, P., Uscola, M. & Heredia Guerrero, N. 2013. *Quercus coccifera* L. In: Pemán, J., Navarro-Cerrillo, R.M., Nicolás, J.L., Prada, M.A. & Serrada, R. (eds.). *Producción y Manejo de Semillas y Plantas Forestales*. Organismo Autónomo Parques Nacionales, pp. 192-205.
- Vitelli, M., Vessella, F., Cardoni, S., Pollegioni, P., Denk, T., Grimm, G.W. & Simeone, M.C. 2017. Phylogeographic structuring of plastome diversity in Mediterranean oaks (*Quercus* Group Ilex, Fagaceae). *Tree Genetics & Genomes*. doi: 10.1007/s11295-016-1086-8.
- Vicente, A.M. & Alés, R.F. 2006. Long term persistence of dehesas. *Agroforestry Systems* 67: 19-28.
- Vuk, M. & Curk, T. 2006. ROC curve. Lift chart and calibration plot. *Metodološki zvezki* 3: 89–108.

Electronic appendices

Additional supporting information as Electronic Appendices may be found in the online version of this article:

EA1. Potential distribution of *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex* in the present period (EA1a) and in the forecasted scenarios (EA1b). Blue colour denotes absence potentiality, whereas yellow and red colours indicate intermediate and high potentiality respectively (see scale in EA1a).

EA2. Potential distribution of *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* in the present period (EA2a) and in the forecasted scenarios (EA2b). Follow the description of the colours in EA1 or see scale in EA2a.

EA3. Potential distribution of *Q. suber* in the present period (EA3a) and in the forecasted scenarios (EA3b). Follow the description of the colours in EA1 or see scale in EA3a.

EA4. Potential distribution of *Q. coccifera* in the present period (EA4a) and in the forecasted scenarios (EA4b). Follow the description of the colours in EA1 or see scale in EA4a.

Figure captions

Fig. 1. Current distribution of the four taxa studied: **a** *Q. coccifera*, **b** *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex*, **c** *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* and, **d** *Q. suber*. Occurrence data was retrieved from each National Forest Inventory (NFI)

Fig. 2 a Suitability and cosuitability among evergreen oaks is shown for the present period (1960–1990). This map is derived from modelling single species, **b** suitability and cosuitability among evergreen oaks is shown for the forecasted scenarios. This map is derived from modelling single species. Legend abbreviations are as follows: Qile (*Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex*), Qbal (*Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*), Qsub (*Q. suber*) and Qcoc (*Q. coccifera*)

a**Present**

Variable	Label	Source
Annual Mean Temperature (°C)	Bio1	WorldClim
Mean Diurnal Range (°C)	Bio2	WorldClim
Isothermality (Bio2/Bio7) x 100	Bio3	WorldClim
Temperature Seasonality (SDx100) (°C)	Bio4	WorldClim
Max Temperature of Warmest Month (°C)	Bio5	WorldClim
Min Temperature of Coldest Month (°C)	Bio6	WorldClim
Temperature Annual Range (°C)	Bio7	WorldClim
Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter (°C)	Bio8	WorldClim
Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter (°C)	Bio9	WorldClim
Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter (°C)	Bio10	WorldClim
Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter (°C)	Bio11	WorldClim
Annual Precipitation (mm)	Bio12	WorldClim
Precipitation of Wettest Month (mm)	Bio13	WorldClim
Precipitation of Driest Month (mm)	Bio14	WorldClim
Precipitation Seasonality (Coeff. of variation)	Bio15	WorldClim
Precipitation of Wettest Quarter (mm)	Bio16	WorldClim
Precipitation of Driest Quarter (mm)	Bio17	WorldClim
Precipitation of Warmest Quarter (mm)	Bio18	WorldClim
Precipitation of Coldest Quarter (mm)	Bio19	WorldClim
Emberger index	Q	WorldClim

Table 1.- Variables used for modelling.

Algorithm	Abbreviation	Statistical technique	Software
Maximum Entropy	MaxEnt	Profile methods	MaxEnt SDM 3.3.3k
Logistic Regression	LR	Regression-based and multivariate	SPSS Statistics 20
Environmental Distance	EnvDis	Machine learning	openModeller 1.5.0

Table 2.- Main characteristics of the algorithms used.

	Present	RCP4.5 2050	RCP4.5 2070	RCP8.5 2050	RCP8.5 2070
<i>Q. ilex</i> subsp. <i>ilex</i>	204.32	683.44	822.31	737.78	788.37
<i>Q. ilex</i> subsp. <i>ballota</i>	340.26	675.42	792.77	734.38	807.40
<i>Q. suber</i>	178.69	550.54	578.27	552.27	600.78
<i>Q. coccifera</i>	407.25	715.01	772.56	764.56	774.79

Table 3.- Predicted surface (x 10³ km²) for the consensus maps of the evergreen oaks.

	MaxEnt	BLR	EnvDis
<i>Q. ilex</i> subsp. <i>ilex</i>	0.76	0.95	0.92
<i>Q. ilex</i> subsp. <i>ballota</i>	0.74	0.92	0.88
<i>Q. suber</i>	0.76	0.93	0.93
<i>Q. coccifera</i>	0.75	0.89	0.93

Table 4.- AUC values to each taxa and algorithm

	Present	RCP4.5 2050	RCP4.5 2070	RCP8.5 2050	RCP8.5 2070
Dominance of Qsub	62.93	30.76	31.11	31.13	32.89
Dominance of Qbal	43.73	9.07	13.11	12.80	16.16
Dominance of Qile	136.18	209.00	205.96	185.15	201.89
Dominance of Qcoc	53.89	10.95	9.39	9.46	11.41
Codominance Qsub-Qbal	7.69	1.10	1.30	1.05	0.99
Codominance Qsub-Qile	22.89	74.76	87.54	81.45	88.81
Codominance Qsub-Qcoc	15.58	23.17	23.95	25.03	23.67
Codominance Qbal-Qile	1.02	45.19	68.68	36.20	97.92
Codominance Qbal-Qcoc	219.83	236.36	235.91	242.55	234.34

Codominance Qile-Qcoc	42.06	18.97	17.87	25.89	19.76
Codominance Qbal-Qile-Qcoc	6.58	175.31	245.73	235.27	250.33
Codominance Qsub-Qile-Qcoc	21.71	63.89	62.72	58.98	62.79
Codominance Qsub-Qbal-Qcoc	54.20	76.42	84.15	78.08	82.88
Codominance Qsub-Qbal-Qile	0.13	3.16	6.16	7.05	5.92
Codominance Qsub-Qbal-Qile-Qcoc	1.29	94.99	69.53	98.64	85.98
Absence (grids under 50 for all the taxa)	759.10	376.33	286.32	320.70	233.69

Table 5.- Predicted surface (x 10³ km²) for the dominance maps of the evergreen oaks.